

Differentiation between Carbon Corrosion and Oxygen Evolution Catalyzed by Ni_xB/C Hybrid Electrocatalysts in Alkaline Solution using Differential Electrochemical Mass Spectrometry

Sandra Möller,^[a] Stefan Barwe,^[a] Stefan Dieckhöfer,^[a] Justus Masa,^[b] Corina Andronescu,^{*,[c]} and Wolfgang Schuhmann^{*,[a]}

Carbon is a frequently used electrode material and an important additive in catalyst films. Its corrosion is often reported during electrocatalysis at high anodic potentials, especially in acidic electrolyte. Investigation of the carbon corrosion in alkaline environment is difficult due to the CO₂/CO₃²⁻ equilibrium. We report the on-line determination of electrolysis products generated on Ni_xB/C hybrid electrocatalysts in alkaline electrolyte at anodic potentials using differential electrochemical mass spectrometry (DEMS). Ni_xB/C catalyst films

were obtained from mixtures containing different ratios of Ni_xB and benzoxazine monomers followed by polymerization and pyrolysis. The impact of the composition of the electrocatalyst on the dominant electrolysis process allows to distinguish between the oxygen evolution reaction and carbon corrosion using DEMS results as well as the catalyst surface composition evaluated from X-ray photoelectron spectra. At the imposed highly oxidative conditions, an increasing amount of Ni_xB in the electrocatalyst leads to a suppression of carbon corrosion.

1. Introduction

In electrocatalysis catalytically active materials often consist of or at least contain a significant amount of carbon as additives or as electrode material. Carbon materials are employed to achieve higher surface areas, to reduce the amount of catalyst, to improve electrical conductivity of poorly conductive catalysts, and to stabilize catalyst particles on electrodes.^[1] However, thermodynamic considerations paired with the harsh conditions during electrochemical water splitting point towards a high likelihood that carbonaceous materials undergo corrosion through dissolution, gasification, or exfoliation under formation of corrosion products.^[2–5] Such processes would affect the carbon properties substantially, and typical consequences of carbon corrosion are the loss of electrochemically active surface area (ECSA), loss of electrical conductivity and a decreased stability of the overall catalyst film. The equilibrium potential of carbon is 0.207 V vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) which

makes it thermodynamically unstable at the potentials higher than 1.23 V vs. RHE necessary for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER).^[3,5] Carbon corrosion can result in numerous soluble and insoluble products of organic and inorganic nature.^[2,4,5] Typical oxidation products such as CO and CO₂ [eqs. (1), (2)] are expected besides other oxidation products like graphite oxides and surface oxygen groups (C=O, C–O–C, O–C=O),^[6] soluble organic products, such as mellitic and humic acids, which are formed in very low concentrations. However, CO formation is thermodynamically hindered due to its higher equilibrium potential, whereas carbon oxidation to CO₂ is favored by a lower standard potential of –0.103 V vs. SHE [eq. (3)].

Despite being well investigated in acidic environment for proton exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cells and electrolyzer technologies,^[7] carbon corrosion processes in alkaline media still lack understanding. Except few reports mainly from the 1980s, carbon corrosion during alkaline OER is only rarely investigated.^[8] One crucial factor hampering especially the detection of CO₂ as the ultimate corrosion product is its fast reaction with hydroxide ions to form carbonate ions [eq. (4)].^[9]

[a] Dr. S. Möller, Dr. S. Barwe, S. Dieckhöfer, Prof. Dr. W. Schuhmann
Analytical Chemistry – Center for Electrochemical Sciences (CES)
Faculty of Chemistry and Biochemistry, Ruhr-University Bochum
Universitätsstr. 150, 44780 Bochum, Germany
E-mail: wolfgang.schuhmann@rub.de

[b] Dr. J. Masa
Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion
Stiftstr. 34–36, D-45470 Mülheim an der Ruhr, Germany

[c] Prof. Dr. C. Andronescu
Technical Chemistry III and CENIDE; Faculty of Chemistry, University
Duisburg-Essen
Universitätsstr. 7, 45141, Essen, Germany
E-mail: corina.andronescu@uni-due.de

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Thus, investigations of carbon corrosion in alkaline media focus on corrosion products different than CO_2 . By following carbon corrosion in alkaline electrolyte by means of spectroscopic methods Yi et al. discovered, that glassy carbon dissolves at highly anodic potential. They proposed a radical mechanism in which the edges of small graphitic domains are oxidized and hence become hydrophilic and finally dissolve in the electrolyte.^[10]

In a previous publication we presented the development of a new electrochemical cell which allowed the in-situ acidification of the electrolyte favoring thus CO_2 release from CO_3^{2-} in front of the DEMS membrane allowing thus CO_2 detection in the mass spectrometer.^[11] We demonstrated that common carbon additives used for the formulation of catalyst inks such as Vulcan XC 72, can undergo corrosion in alkaline environment, but the process is considerable diminished in the presence of highly active OER electrocatalysts such as e.g. Ni_xB . The high OER activity of Ni_xB is due to the in-situ formation of a thin layer of the active species NiOOH around the conductive Ni_xB nanoparticle generating thus an active electrocatalyst with increased conductivity.^[12]

We also introduced polybenzoxazines as precursor for the synthesis of hybrid electrocatalyst materials with increased stability during the OER.^[13,14,15] The catalyst synthesis involves mixing of the organic benzoxazine monomer with a precursor or an active OER electrocatalyst, followed by pyrolysis of the mixture deposited directly on the current collector. Compared with the traditional methods presently used for catalyst immobilization, which usually involve the deposition of an ink containing a mixture of catalyst, carbon and binders on the current collector, this approach has two major advantages. The direct formation of the catalyst layer on the current collector allows a more stable layer immobilization and decreased detachment of the catalyst. In addition, the catalyst is homogeneously distributed within the conductive carbon matrix, which is very important for active phases consisting of transition metal oxyhydroxides which are known to have poor conductivity. Despite the promising performance of the modified electrodes at high current density,^[13,15] carbon corrosion from the catalyst layer at the high OER potentials and hence catalyst stability need to be investigated.

Here, Ni_xB embedded in a carbon matrix generated via pyrolysis of polybenzoxazine hybrid composites is used for the investigation of carbon corrosion in alkaline environment using the previous developed electrochemical cell in combination with DEMS. The influence of the ratio between the active catalyst (Ni_xB) and the benzoxazine precursor (BO) on the balance between oxygen evolution reaction and carbon corrosion will be presented.

2. Results and Discussion

$\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ modified electrodes were prepared by drop coating of glassy carbon (GC) electrodes with mixtures containing different ratios between the Ni_xB and BO. For Ni_xB modified GC a mass loading of 0.21 mg cm^{-2} was used, while for the hybrid

electrocatalysts the amount of BO was maintained constant while the amount of Ni_xB was adjusted accordingly to generate inks with 0.3, 1.5 and 5 wt.% Ni_xB (relative to the amount of BO). A step heating procedure was applied to the coated electrodes for 2 h at 180°C , 200°C and finally at 600°C in Ar atmosphere. During the first two heating steps polymerization of BO monomers into a crosslinked network of polybenzoxazine (pBO) takes place generating a hybrid material consisting of $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$. In the last heating step, pyrolysis of the carbonaceous part of the composite occurs with the generation of a conductive N-doped carbon matrix in which the active OER electrocatalyst, Ni_xB , is embedded and stably immobilized on the electrode surface. The weight of the catalyst coated GC was determined before and after pyrolysis revealing that an average of $76.5 \pm 2.5 \text{ wt. \%}$ was lost during pyrolysis. The mass loss corresponds to the degradation of the pBO into N-doped carbon is in line with previous findings in which a residual char of 27 wt. % was reported after pyrolysis of the pBO alone for 2 h at 600°C in Ar atmosphere.^[13] The labels of the catalysts in the following paragraphs will take the initial ratio between the Ni_xB and the BO monomer into consideration, and will have the following format: $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-0.3$, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-1.5$ and $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-5.0$.

The modified electrodes were electrochemically evaluated in 0.1 M KOH using a protocol which involves first an activation step in which the potential is cycled from 1 to 1.6 V vs. RHE followed by a series of sequential measurements composed of one cyclic voltammogram (CV), 3 min chronopotentiometry (CP) at 4.8 mA corresponding to a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2} and again one CV. The procedure was repeated several times until the potentials recorded during the last two CPs had similar values.

The CP measurements depicted in Figure 1 show that for the only pBO (Fig 1a) or Ni_xB (Fig 1e) coated electrodes, the potential recorded during consecutive CPs is similar, having just slight variations between CP1 and CP2 indicating that the electrodes reach a stable operation regime in a relative short time. It is important to mention that the same current density is leading to completely different potentials for pBO or Ni_xB with $\sim 2.4 \text{ V}$ and 1.65 V vs. RHE, respectively. For the hybrid catalysts, depending on the initial $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ ratio, a stable potential can be achieved after 2 to 6 CPs. In all cases, in the first CP potentials higher than 2.4 V vs. RHE are recorded with a dramatic decrease in the second CP. This indicates that in the first CP a different electrochemical process occurs compared with the following measurements.

For catalysts with high Ni_xB loading ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-5.0$ (Figure 1c) and $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-1.5$ (Figure 1d)), a fast decrease in the potential is observed, and a stable potential is achieved after 3 or 5 CPs, respectively, reaching values lower than 1.8 V vs. RHE. For the low-content Ni_xB catalyst ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-0.3$ (Figure 1e)) the decay is slower, and after 6 CPs still a potential of $\sim 2.2 \text{ V}$ vs. RHE is recorded. This indicates that the processes occurring on the hybrid electrocatalysts are a combination of the processes catalyzed by Ni_xB and pBO alone.

To understand to which extent OER or carbon corrosion occurs, DEMS measurements (Figure 2) were performed and the ion current corresponding to CO_2 ($m/z=44$, black) as well as O_2

Figure 1. Summary of the chronopotentiometric measurements recorded while applying 4.8 mA (13.3 mA cm^{-2}) in 0.1 M KOH for different catalysts modified electrodes. The electrolyte flow rate in the DEMS cell was $270 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$.

($m/z = 32$, red) were monitored while applying a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2} . For detection of CO_2 , 0.15 M H_2SO_4 was introduced at the additional electrolyte inlet over the duration of the experiment using the previously described DEMS electrochemical cell (Figure 2).^[11] Due to the specific cell design, containing a channel into which H_2SO_4 is injected to release the previously formed CO_3^{2-} derived from CO_2 in the alkaline environment between the working electrode chamber and the DEMS membrane, a delay between the electrochemical signals and the ion currents recorded in the MS is observed. For Ni_xB coated GC (Figure 2a), O_2 was the only detected product, and this was expected since no carbon-based additive was added during the coating process. Contrary, in the case of pBO coated electrode (Figure 2b), in the first CP just CO_2 is observed, while no O_2 is recorded. Starting from CP2, O_2 is also detected together with CO_2 . This indicates that in the first CP, carbon corrosion is the dominant process and the already partially oxidized carbon which may be formed during the pyrolysis process is removed from the electrode surface. In the following second CP, carbon corrosion is still the dominant process, but OER starts also to take place. For the high Ni_xB content hybrid electrocatalyst ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-5.0$ (Figure 2c)) in the initial CP both O_2 and CO_2 are observed, which indicates that both OER and carbon corrosion occur simultaneously. Interestingly, after the second CP no further CO_2 is detected while for O_2 an increase in the signal is observed. This indicates that after initial corrosion of the covering carbon at potentials higher than 2.2 V vs. RHE, the active OER centers are exposed to the electrolyte. Hence, the only reaction which takes place is then the OER at potentials of $\sim 1.6 \text{ V}$ vs. RHE, while no further carbon corrosion is noticed. A further decrease of Ni_xB content in the hybrid catalyst to $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-1.5$ (Figure 2d) shows a similar result, however, as expected in this case a longer carbon corrosion time is required until all carbon which covers the Ni_xB sites is removed. In the 4th CP an increase in the O_2 signal is recorded concomitant with the complete decrease of CO_2 signal, indicating that no carbon corrosion occurs any longer. Notably an even lower content of Ni_xB in the hybrid electrocatalyst

($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-0.3$ (Fig 2e)) leads to a concomitant production of O_2 and CO_2 even after multiple CPs, indicating that such electrocatalysts do not have enough OER active center distributed in the carbon matrix and would develop severe instability issues over time. Based on the results presented in Figures 1 and 2 we can conclude that carbon corrosion occurs from the hybrid $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ electrocatalysts synthesized via pyrolysis until active OER catalytic centers are exposed and oxygen evolution can occur. The possible mechanism of the processes occurring on the catalyst surface is presented in Scheme 1. Depending on the ratio of catalyst and carbon matrix, carbon corrosion and OER can occur simultaneously, or just OER can be observed, while carbon corrosion is suppressed. This confirms that carbon corrosion in alkaline solution is substantially suppressed if a highly active OER catalyst is able to provide sufficient activity to satisfy the galvanostatically applied current density.

To further confirm this, the comparison of potentials at which a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2} is maintained during the 3rd CP using the pBO and Ni_xB alone or the hybrid

Scheme 1. Schematic distribution of the active OER electrocatalyst, in this case Ni_xB , in a N-doped carbon matrix generated by pyrolysis of $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ hybrid electrocatalysts depending on the Ni_xB to BO ratio. The expected electrochemical processes which can occur at early and prolonged electrolysis times in dependence on the $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ composition are presented.

Figure 2. Measurement sequence for the determination of CO_2 and O_2 . A combined sequence consisting of a CV followed by a chronopotentiometric measurement at a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2} for 3 min each followed by a second CV was repeated several times in 0.1 M KOH using the catalyst coated GC. For the in situ acidification, 0.15 M H_2SO_4 solution was introduced to the additional electrolyte inlet over time to allow the CO_2 detection. Top: ion signal for CO_2 (i_{CO_2} , black, left ordinate axis). Below: ion signal for O_2 (i_{O_2} , red, left ordinate axis) versus time. The potential against RHE is plotted in grey (right ordinate axis) against time. The electrolyte flow rate was $270 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$.

electrocatalysts is presented in Figure 3. The 3rd CP was chosen since all catalysts showed O_2 formation in this CP, independent on the $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ ratio. Interestingly, a direct correlation between the Ni_xB amount and the recorded potentials is observed. While Ni_xB can generate 13.3 mA cm^{-2} at $\sim 1.67 \text{ V}$ vs. RHE, the increased amount of pBO leads to an increased overpotential reaching a value of $\sim 2.5 \text{ V}$ vs. RHE for pBO alone

and $\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}-0.3$. This indicates that the potential at which the electrolysis occurs is strongly impacting on the dominant reaction. When potentials lower than 1.8 V vs. RHE are enough to generate 13.3 mA cm^{-2} no detectable carbon corrosion occurs, while at higher potential values the recorded current is generated by both OER and carbon corrosion.

Figure 3. Comparison of the potential required to achieve a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2} in the 3rd CP using pBO, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-0.3}$, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-1.5}$, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-5.0}$ and Ni_xB coated GC electrodes.

In addition, we also compared the CVs recorded for each catalyst before running the last CP as presented in Figure 2. The CVs recorded for Ni_xB as well as for the high-content Ni_xB hybrid electrocatalysts ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-5.0}$ and $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-1.5}$) have almost identical shape. For Ni_xB and $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-5.0}$ almost identical oxidation peaks are observed at $\sim 1.4 \text{ V}$ vs. RHE which correspond to the $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ transition. This indicates that a similar number of active centers (NiOOH) are formed on the surfaces of these two catalysts. According to Figure 2 a,c no O_2 was detected for these two catalysts in CP3 and CP4 for Ni_xB and $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-5}$, respectively. For $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-1.5}$ we see a decrease in the intensity of the $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ oxidation peak which means that less Ni atoms are exposed on the catalyst surface. According to Figure 2d, the major product obtained on $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-1.5}$ is O_2 but also CO_2 could be observed in low amounts (close to the detection limit). Despite in the potential range of the recorded CV the $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-1.5}$ shows apparently a similar activity compared with Ni_xB , it is possible that at higher current densities the OER active centers are limiting the OER, and carbon corrosion starts to take place. For the $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-0.3}$ almost no $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ oxidation peak can be observed indicating that this material has a much smaller number of Ni atoms presented on the surface. In addition, the catalyst shows a higher electrochemical activity compared with the pure pBO coated electrode but much smaller than all the others Ni_xB based hybrid electrocatalysts. This is in good agreement with the results presented in Figure 2e where CO_2 was one of the detected products together with O_2 .

The surface of the catalyst-coated electrodes after pyrolysis was characterized using XPS before and after performing the DEMS measurements (Figure 5). For all freshly prepared electrodes, the C 1s spectrum shows a dominant peak at a binding energy (BE) of $\sim 284.5 \text{ eV}$ with contributions from both sp^2 and/or sp^3 hybridized carbon. Based on the C 1s spectra no clear oxidation of the surface carbon can be observed after the pyrolysis process for all catalysts. When analyzing the Ni 2p XP spectra, one can notice that for the hybrid electrocatalysts no Ni peak can be identified indicating that immediately after

Figure 4. Comparison of the CVs recorded for pBO, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-0.3}$, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-1.5}$, $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-5.0}$ and Ni_xB coated GC electrodes during the experiment as presented in Figure 2 before running the last CP.

pyrolysis a carbon film is covering the hybrid electrocatalyst surface. After performing DEMS measurements i.e. after applying current densities leading to carbon corrosion and OER, clear changes on the surface of the hybrid electrocatalysts are observed. A partial oxidation of C can be noticed which is more pronounced for pBO alone and for the low Ni_xB content hybrid electrocatalyst ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-0.3}$). For all hybrid electrocatalysts, after partial corrosion of carbon from the catalyst surface, Ni sites are exposed as confirmed by the Ni 2p XP spectra. This clearly shows that all hybrid electrocatalysts start to be electrocatalytically active towards OER once the Ni_xB catalyst is exposed to the electrolyte, which is in good agreement with the oxidation peak corresponding to $\text{Ni}^{2+}/\text{Ni}^{3+}$ observed in the CVs presented in Figure 4. Based on the Ni 2p XP spectra of Ni_xB before and after DEMS measurements, a clear change in the oxidation state can be noticed. Before DEMS measurements, Ni is present in a more reduced form corresponding to Ni^0 or Ni-B (BE $\sim 852.8 \text{ eV}$) together with more oxidized species like NiO or Ni(OH)_2 (BE ~ 853.7 and 856.2 eV , respectively). After performing electrocatalysis when the catalyst is exposed to high anodic potentials an increase in oxidized Ni species is observed and the catalyst contains mainly Ni(OH)_2 and NiO on its surface, known to be active OER centers.

3. Conclusions

Using a previously designed DEMS cell, carbon corrosion as well as the OER occurring on hybrid $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/C}$ electrocatalysts was monitored during electrocatalysis performed at anodic potentials in alkaline environment. Initially carbon corrosion occurs for all hybrid electrocatalysts since immediately after pyrolysis a layer of carbon is covering the active OER Ni centers. Competition between OER and carbon corrosion strongly depends on the composition of the hybrid electrocatalysts. For $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-5.0}$ a complete suppression of carbon corrosion is possible while for $\text{Ni}_x\text{B/pBO-0.3}$ carbon corrosion occurs in

parallel with the OER. Hence, an optimum ratio needs to be found to generate stable carbon containing electrocatalysts which catalyze just the OER due to the fact that the OER active sites are dominating the surface composition.

Experimental Section

Chemicals and Materials

Benzoxazine monomer (Araldite 35600 (Huntsman), potassium hydroxide pellets (Carl Roth), sulfuric acid (>95%, Fisher) and ethanol and potassium hydrogen carbonate (Sigma Aldrich) were of analytical grade and used as received unless explicitly stated otherwise. The water used for electrolyte preparation was purified using a water purification system (SG Water) and had a conductivity of $0.055 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$. For the pyrolysis experiments, high-purity Argon was purchased from AirLiquide. Ni_xB used as catalyst precursor was synthesized according to the protocol by Masa et. al.^[12] Glassy carbon electrodes with a diameter of 10 mm (HTW) were used in all electrochemical experiments.

Catalyst Synthesis

The benzoxazine monomer and Ni_xB (synthesized at 300°C according to^[12]) were used as precursors for the synthesis of the final catalysts. Solutions containing different ratios of the benzoxazine and Ni_xB were prepared in ethanol.

The BO starting solution had a concentration of 10 mg mL^{-1} and the Ni_xB starting solution had a concentration of 2 mg mL^{-1} . Different volume ratios of the two solutions were used to obtain inks with Ni_xB contents of 0.3 wt.% ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ -0.3), 1.5 wt.% ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ -1.5) and 5.0 wt.% ($\text{Ni}_x\text{B}/\text{pBO}$ -5.0) in relation to the mass of BO. The mass of the precursor mixture loaded onto the glassy carbon electrodes was determined by weighing of the electrode before and after the drop-coating process. Pyrolysis of the coated electrodes was performed in a tube furnace in an Ar flow using a step heating profile. Using 10 K min^{-1} heating rate the temperature was increased from room temperature (r.t.) to 180°C where the temperature was maintained constant for 2 h before a further increase to 200°C where another 2 h of constant temperature was maintained. During this time, polymerization of the benzoxazine monomer occurs with formation of a crosslinked composite containing Ni_xB embedded in the polybenzoxazine matrix. The final catalyst was obtained by a further increase of the temperature to 600°C which was maintained constant for 2 h to allow decomposition of the polybenzoxazine matrix. The furnace was cooled to r.t. while maintaining a constant Ar flow. For all samples, the mass of carbon was maintained constant to $238.71 \mu\text{g} \pm 12.84 \mu\text{g}$.

X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

XPS analysis was performed on an AXIS Nova spectrometer using a monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ X-ray source (1487 eV, 15 mA emission current). Throughout the measurements, the pressure in the sample analysis chamber was maintained at about 10^{-8} Torr. The spectrometer was operated at constant electron pass energy (20 eV). Charges on the sample surface during the XPS measurements were neutralized with a low energy electron flood gun. The binding energy scale was calibrated according to the C 1s peak at 284.5 eV. Peak fitting of the XPS spectra was done using the ESCAPE software. The Shirley background method was applied for the deconvolution of the Ni 2p signal. An asymmetric function (asymmetry factor of 2) was employed for the metallic Ni⁰

Figure 5. C 1s and Ni 2p XPS spectra of catalyst-coated GC electrodes before (a, c) and after (b, d) chronopotentiometric measurements at a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2} . Comparison of the deconvoluted Ni 2p XPS spectra recorded for Ni_xB before and after DEMS measurements (e) at 13.3 mA cm^{-2} in 0.1 M KOH. All spectra were calibrated using the C 1s peak at 284.5 eV.

component, whereas Gaussian-Lorentzian product functions (GL ratio of 0.3) were utilized for the remaining components.

Differential Electrochemical Mass Spectrometry (DEMS)

DEMS measurements were performed in 0.1 M KOH (flow velocity $270 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$). For CO_2 release 0.15 M H_2SO_4 (flow velocity $270 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) was introduced at the additional electrolyte inlet. For Ni_xB containing electrocatalysts, 20 CVs with 50 mVs^{-1} were run between 1 and 1.6 V vs. RHE, while for pBO alone, just 5 cycles were performed between 1 and 1.7 V vs. RHE. A combined protocol containing a CV, a Cp followed by another CP. This protocol was repeated several times until a stable potential during two consecutive CPs was recorded. The chronopotentiometric (CP) measurements were further performed by applying 4.8 mA (corresponding to a current density of 13.3 mA cm^{-2}) for 3 min. Before and after each CP measurement a CV in a potential range from 1.0 V to 1.7 V vs. RHE was recorded. All potentials are corrected for the uncompensated solution resistance evaluated from electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) recorded at open-circuit potential in 0.1 M KOH in a frequency range from 200 kHz to 1 Hz using an ac amplitude of 10 mV_{pp} . By introducing an Ar flow, gas bubbles were removed from the working electrode. The ion current corresponding to CO_2 ($m/z=44$) and O_2 ($m/z=32$) was monitored using a GAM 400 mass spectrometer from

InProcess Instruments. All experiments were performed using a custom-built electrochemical cell which can be coupled to the MS and which allows for the in-situ acidification of the electrolyte and thus the release of possibly formed CO₂ from CO₃²⁻. All details regarding the design of the DEMS cell as well as the calibration of the MS are presented in our previous publication.^[11]

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords: differential electrochemical mass spectrometry · DEMS · hybrid electrocatalysts · carbon corrosion · oxygen evolution reaction

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